

Numerical Investigation of CO₂ Solubility in brine during Continuous CO₂ flooding and optimization of different parameters

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Abstract-- A huge volume of crude oil, after conventional primary and secondary oil recovery mechanisms are left behind in reservoir. To produce this crude oil, currently many tertiary enhanced oil recovery mechanisms are in design and operation stage. Due to the global demand of crude oil and its high prices, it developed a great interest in enhanced oil recovery mechanisms. Injecting gas is a reasonable method to enhance oil recovery because of the low viscosity of the gas and least formation damage caused by the gas. Compared to other gases carbon dioxide flooding is the second method used widely in the world to maximize the production. Especially when the reservoir pressure is depleted during primary and secondary recovery mechanism. CO₂ flooding can be used both in sandstone and carbonate formations. Due to the increased amount of carbon dioxide concentration and its effect on the global warming, Carbon dioxide flooding achieved more potential for future growth by reducing carbon dioxide emission from many sources and can extract additional oil from the reservoirs and can reduce greenhouse effect. Therefore, in this study the main focus is to conduct a comprehensive study on CO₂ solubility during its flooding to improve oil recovery and the effect of the pressure, temperature and CO₂ concentration on the CO₂ solubility and to optimize different parameters and its effect on oil recovery during CO₂ flooding. CO₂ solubility in brine is a function of both pressure and temperature. Brine concentration has also effect on solubility. For this purpose an ideal reservoir model is prepared for XYZ field using synthetic data and using CMG GEM module.

Keywords- CO₂ Flooding; Optimization; Enhanced Oil Recovery; CO₂ Solubility; CMG GEM

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I.INTRODUCTION

After the two oil recovery processes primary and secondary more than 50% oil remains in the reservoir. This remaining amount of oil left can be produced by applying tertiary enhanced oil recovery methods for future years to come. Due to worldwide oil demand and increased oil prices application of enhanced oil recovery methods are increasing day by day [1]. The survey conducted every year by (Moriti) oil and Gas Journal shows the production in U.S.A. and Canada is about 10% and 25% respectively obtained by applying EOR methods [2]. The variation in reservoir characteristics plays main role in the selection of EOR technique to get the production from the current existing field. Selection of EOR method also depends on the financial value of the project which is going to be applied [3]. After Whorton and Brownscombe obtained obvious result

for oil recovery process by using CO₂ the awareness of using CO₂ to enhance crude oil recovery was suggested in 1950's from that time till to date this method got large importance for crude oil recovery [4]. In the recent period the implementation of tertiary enhanced oil recovery is grown-up fast in the fields which are near to their depletion stage. Among tertiary enhanced oil recovery techniques CO₂ flooding is best method in depleted reservoirs having residual oil saturation greater than 25%, having API gravity more than 22° and depth greater than 800 meter [5] [6]. Under most reservoir conditions CO₂ acts like a supercritical fluid. A matter above its critical pressure and temperature where its distinct gas and liquid phase do not exist. CO₂ at supercritical point can effuse through solids similar to gas and dissolve materials similar to liquid. At critical point CO₂ viscosity is 0.0335 cp which is greater than other possible injection gases [7]. Chemical and physical reactions takes place when CO₂ is introduced into the reservoir it will lead to interact with oil and rock. This method will develop the following suitable conditions;

1. Due to decrease of IFT between the formation and the oil, the capillary pressure is reduced and will cause easier flow of oil.

2. Once CO₂ is dissolved in oil it will expand and will decrease the viscosity of the oil as well [8].

The use of CO₂ as an enhanced oil recovery method is also more attractive because of global warming. CO₂ flooding into oil reservoirs have some important aims like CO₂ sequestration, enhance residual oil saturation and production of methane from hydrates. Oil production from CO₂ flooding is improved by swelling the oil, decreasing viscosity [9]. Using CO₂ as an injecting fluid it can dissolve heavier constituents of crude oil up to C₃₀. When CO₂ is dissolved in crude oil it will cause oil swelling and will expand the crude oil [10]. The increase in oil recovery is observed due to the following advantages of CO₂ flooding:

- Swelling of the oil is increased
- Oil density is increased
- Oil viscosity is decreased
- CO₂ injection will decrease interfacial tension among water and oil and will reduce the capillary force and will increase oil displacement.
- The density difference among oil and water is minimized and therefore it will decrease the gravity segregation.

The amount of increase in average surface temperature is attributed to the rise of CO₂ emission in the atmosphere. One of the method to reduce global warming is to capture CO₂ from bulky point sources and store into geological formations[11]. By using CO₂ as an enhanced oil recovery process the effect of CO₂ on global warming can be reduced and in addition it will provide us the additional energy. This method is called carbon capture utilization and storage and plays a vigorous role globally [12]. CO₂ flooding also obtained more importance due to the reduction of CO₂ emission from many industrial sources, due to which the availability of CO₂ at economic cost will be increased [13]. There are four important mechanisms on which the extensive storage of carbon dioxide sequestration depends, they are stratigraphic and structural trapping, residual carbon dioxide trapping, mineral and solubility trapping [14][15]. The solubility trapping involves a portion of the injected CO₂ that will dissolve into the brine water which is already present in the pore spaces within the rock[16]. For CO₂ storage, the storage ability and features of saline aquifers mark them an appropriate candidate. A brine aquifer is frequently composed of sandstone and carbonates[17].

In this research Henry's law for the solubility of CO₂ in brine is used. CO₂ solubility in brine is a reversible reaction as shown below;

The fugacities of carbon dioxide in both aqueous and gas phase must be equal for the thermodynamic equilibrium to occur, That is;

$$fCO_{2(g)} = fCO_{2(w)}$$

To compute the gas phase fugacity equation of state is used and it cannot properly model the aqueous phase fugacity. Due to this reason Henry's law is applied to calculate fugacity of carbon dioxide in aqueous phase.

$$fCO_{2(w)} = y CO_{2(w)} HCO_{2(w)}$$

Henry's law basically is a gas law which states that quantity of dissolved gas is proportionate to partial pressure in gas phase. The proportionality constant which is so-called as Henry's constant, $HCO_{2(w)}$ is dependent on salinity at the reservoir temperature [16]. During the solubility of CO₂ in the brine molar volume, reference pressure at infinite dilution and Henry's constant are properties to be calculated [18].

Henry's constant is calculated from the following relation;

$$\ln H_i = \ln H_i^o + \frac{v_i^\infty (p - p_i^o)}{RT}$$

Where;

P_i^o is reference pressure

V_i^∞ is molar volume

H is Henry's constant at reference pressure

In this research work the total salinity of saline water is considered to be composed of Na⁺ and Cl⁻ ions and the total salinity of the saline water is considered as 100,000 ppm.

II.SIMULATION SECTION

A. Fluid Data

The fluid compositional data is presented in Table I. Reservoir initial pressure is 3700 psi and the other data of the reservoir is presented in Table II.

TABLE I
Fluid compositional data

Component	Compositions
CO ₂	0.00126
N ₂	0.00345
CH ₄	0.37545
C ₂ H ₆	0.05153
C ₃ H ₈	0.02313
IC ₄	0.02138
NC ₄	0.01534
IC ₅	0.01847
NC ₅	0.04528
FC ₆	0.04029
FC ₇₊	0.40441

TABLE II
Reservoir data

Reservoir Properties	Values
Reservoir Temperature	225 °F
Initial Reservoir pressure	3700 psi
Saturation pressure	2145 psi
Porosity	0.33
Permeability	50 mD
Reservoir depth	5200 ft

B. Simulation Method

The simulation method used in this study is based on by using Peng–Robinson (1978) equation in CMG-winprop. The reservoir fluid composition is inserted and then the saturation pressure is calculated and matched with the reservoir actual reservoir saturation pressure. For solubility of CO₂ in brine and optimization process an ideal model is established in Winprop module and then imported it into GEM.

C. Solubility of CO₂

With the intention to calculate the amount of solubility of CO₂ in saline water the phase behavior model of the fluids is generated in Winprop module of CMG. In this research work the total salinity of saline water is considered to be composed of Na⁺ and Cl⁻ ions and the total salinity of the saline water is considered as 100,000 ppm.

For the solubility of CO₂ the fluid components of the reservoir, their mole fraction and the calculated Henry’s constant at reference pressure and molar volume is given in table III. Henry’s constant is only calculated for water and CO₂, since we are considering the solubility of CO₂ in brine only therefore rest of the components are considered not soluble.

Under different temperature and pressure conditions several results have been generated for the solubility of CO₂ in brine. The obtained results at different pressure and temperature are presented in table IV and in figure 1.

TABLE III
Fluid components of the reservoir for solubility of CO₂ in saline water

Components	Mol.	Ref.Henry	V inf.	P ref
CO ₂	0.00063	2680.59	0.00464	32.321
N ₂	0.00173	Insoluble	0.00484	32.321
CH ₄ toC ₂ H	0.21349	Insoluble	0.00453	32.321
C ₃ HtoNC ₅	0.06180	Insoluble	0.00341	32.321
C ₆ toC ₁₂	0.09898	Insoluble	0.00312	32.321
C ₁₃ toC ₁₉	0.02316	Insoluble	0.00295	32.321
C ₂₀ toC ₂₃	0.02626	Insoluble	0.00290	32.321
C ₂₄ +	0.07396	Insoluble	0.00289	32.321
H ₂ O	0.50000	0.13	0.01822	32.321

TABLE IV
Solubility of CO₂ in saline water at different pressure and

Pressure	temperature								
	75 °F	100	125	150	175	200	225 °F	250 °F	275 °F
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
475	1.27	0.87	0.65	0.52	0.44	0.39	0.36	0.33	0.31
975	1.88	1.39	1.09	0.90	0.79	0.71	0.67	0.64	0.62
1475	1.95	1.57	1.31	1.13	1.01	0.94	0.89	0.87	0.86
1975	2.00	1.62	1.39	1.25	1.15	1.09	1.06	1.05	1.06
2475	2.05	1.66	1.44	1.31	1.24	1.20	1.18	1.192	1.21
2975	2.09	1.70	1.48	1.35	1.29	1.26	1.27	1.29	1.33
3475	2.13	1.74	1.52	1.39	1.33	1.31	1.32	1.36	1.41
3975	2.17	1.78	1.55	1.43	1.37	1.36	1.38	1.42	1.48
4475	2.20	1.81	1.59	1.47	1.41	1.4	1.42	1.47	1.54
4975	2.24	1.84	1.62	1.50	1.45	1.44	1.47	1.52	1.60
5475	2.27	1.87	1.65	1.53	1.48	1.48	1.51	1.57	1.65
5975	2.30	1.90	1.67	1.56	1.51	1.51	1.55	1.61	1.70
6475	2.32	1.92	1.70	1.59	1.54	1.54	1.58	1.65	1.75
6975	2.35	1.95	1.73	1.61	1.57	1.57	1.62	1.69	1.79
7475	2.37	1.97	1.75	1.63	1.59	1.60	1.65	1.73	1.84

Fig. 1. Solubility of CO₂ at different temperature and pressure

From results of solubility of CO₂ at different temperature and pressure it can be observed that solubility increases with decrease in temperature and when the temperature value is higher than 200 ° F the trend of the curve changes at a pressure of 2500 psia, at this point the trend show that solubility increase with increase in temperature. Because initially reservoir was having three phases liquid, aqueous and vapour but when the pressure and temperature increased the liquid phase starts evaporating, and the reservoir is having two phases vapour phase and aqueous phase at higher pressure and temperature. And the reservoir fluid phase behavior changed to two phase at a pressure above 2500 psia.

From the results of the graph it can also be determined that solubility rises with increase in pressure. Similarly several

results have been generated for the solubility of CO₂ in brine at different brine concentration and pressure conditions. The obtained results at different brine concentration and pressure are presented in table V and in figure 2.

TABLE V
Solubility of CO₂ in saline water at different brine concentration and pressure

Pressure (Psi)	Brine Concentration (PPM)						
	50000	100000	150000	200000	250000	300000	350000
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
475	0.65	0.53	0.41	0.31	0.23	0.16464	0.10979
975	1.09	0.88	0.69	0.52	0.38	0.27371	0.18253
1475	1.31	1.05	0.83	0.63	0.46	0.32814	0.21882
1975	1.39	1.12	0.88	0.67	0.49	0.34953	0.23309
2475	1.44	1.16	0.91	0.69	0.51	0.36116	0.24085
2975	1.48	1.19	0.94	0.71	0.52	0.37165	0.24784
3475	1.52	1.22	0.96	0.73	0.54	0.38128	0.25427
3975	1.55	1.25	0.98	0.75	0.55	0.39021	0.26022
4475	1.59244	1.28	1.00	0.76	0.56	0.39852	0.26576
4975	1.62346	1.30	1.028	0.78	0.57	0.40629	0.27095
5475	1.65257	1.33	1.04	0.79	0.58	0.41359	0.27581
5975	1.67996	1.35	1.06	0.81	0.59	0.42045	0.28039
6475	1.70578	1.37	1.08	0.82	0.60	0.42692	0.2847
6975	1.73016	1.39	1.09	0.83	0.61	0.43303	0.28878
7475	1.75321	1.41	1.11	0.84	0.62	0.4388	0.29263

Fig. 2. Solubility at 125 °F at different brine concentration of CO₂

From the above results it can be concluded that the solubility rises with decrease in the amount of salinity of the brine without considering the pressure and temperature effects at different amount of brine salinity. Therefore from the results obtained from figure 2 and figure 3 we can conclude that solubility in the saline aquifer basically depends on temperature, pressure and salinity. Figure 3 shows the percent of carbon dioxide solubility at different brine concentration as a function of the salinity of the brine.

Fig. 3. Solubility of CO₂ in Brine at different NaCl Concentration

The Winprop generated model for solubility of CO₂ is imported into builder module to check its behavior during CO₂ injection for improving oil recovery. The result is shown in figure 4. From the result it can be observed that when CO₂ is injected after secondary recovery process improves oil recovery and it also produces the oil left after water flooding. From the result of the graph it can also be concluded that the gas recovery factor has a positive trend during primary and secondary recovery process. It is due to the amount of dissolved gas in the oil, coming out with produced oil as a gas oil ratio. But when CO₂ is injected during tertiary recovery process the gas recovery factor trend is changed. The trend of gas recovery factor has negative behavior which shows that carbon dioxide is dissolved in the brine. Meanwhile CO₂ improves oil recovery and it is also sequestered in the saline water.

Fig. 4. Solubility of Carbon dioxide in Brine

D. Optimization

For the optimization of different parameters an ideal reservoir model is established in compositional module (GEM). In which CO₂ is injected after the primary and secondary recovery methods. The reservoir model of grids size 31×31×15 was established. The depth of 1st layer of SHZ sandstone reservoir is 5200 ft. and the water oil contact is at 5350ft.

D.1 Optimization of well pattern

With the aim to evaluate the influence of well pattern on oil recovery in the same reservoir volume, simulation of primary, secondary and CO₂ flooding is performed in different well patterns. With the intention to evaluate the effect of well pattern having the same reservoir volume on oil recovery every parameter of the reservoir fluid are kept constant in every well pattern. The different well pattern having the same reservoir volume are shown in figure 5.

Fig. 5. 5-Spot, 7-Spot and 9-Spot well pattern respectively

After completing the three recovery phases in above well patterns the result is obtained between daily oil rate and oil recovery factor which is displayed in figure 6. The result between well pattern and oil recovery factor is presented in figure 7. From the trend of the graph it is observed that the oil recovery factor for 7-spot well pattern is higher than 5-spot and 9-spot well pattern. The recovery factor for 7-spot is higher than other well patterns because the well distance of the production wells are larger from the injection wells as compared to the 5-spot and 9-spot well pattern. As a result the sweep efficiency of water and CO₂ injection is better. The oil saturation and displacement of oil during H₂O and CO₂ flooding in the reservoir, in 7-spot well pattern is presented in figure 8.

Fig. 6. Daily oil rate and recovery factor for 5, 7 and 9-spot well pattern

Fig. 7. Oil recovery factor comparison for different well patterns

Fig. 8. Oil saturation and displacement of oil during H₂O and CO₂ Flooding in 7-Spot well pattern

D.2 Well distance

After the simulation of different well patterns for the same reservoir volume, it was observed that 7-spot well pattern has the maximum oil recovery factor. So 7-spot well pattern is used to study the influence of well distance on oil recovery. For this purpose 7-spot well pattern models were established at six different distances that is 293m, 257m, 222m, 187m, 152, and at 117m from the injection wells. After completing the three recovery phases at different well distances the daily oil rate is plotted against the oil recovery factor for all the six cases as shown in figure 9 and the graphical result of oil recovery factor at different well distance is presented in figure 10.

Fig. 9. Oil recovery factor versus daily oil rate at different well distance

Fig. 10. Oil recovery factor versus daily oil rate at different well distance

From the result of the graph it can be observed that maximum oil recovery factor is obtained for this model is at 257 meter well distance from the injection well. From the result it can also be concluded when the distance is close to the injection well in the start the sweep efficiency is good but later due to close distance the water and CO₂ starts producing. But when the distance is far like at 293 meter from the injection well the oil recovery factor is not higher as compare to the wells at a distance of 257 meter. It is because of the larger distance from the injection wells there effect is not felt effectively to sweep the oil during water and CO₂ injection.

D.3 CO₂ Concentration on Oil Recovery

After selecting the appropriate well pattern, well distance the influence of CO₂ concentration on oil recovery is studied. In this case a simulation study is performed to show the effect of CO₂ on oil recovery. For this purpose different CO₂ concentration are used which are 100%, 95%, 90%, 85%, 80%, 75%, 70%, 65% and 60% along with different nitrogen amount as an injected gas as shown in the table VI and the obtained result is presented in figure 11. Result of oil recovery factor is plotted for different CO₂ concentration which is presented in figure 12.

Fig. 11. Oil recovery factor at different CO₂ concentration

Fig. 12. Different CO₂ concentration versus oil recovery factor

From the result of the graph it can be concluded that the oil recovery factor value is higher when the CO₂ concentration is high.

TABLE VI

Injected Gas Concentration

Composition	Injected Gas Concentration								
	100	95	90	85	80	75	70	65	60
CO ₂ (%)	100	95	90	85	80	75	70	65	60
N ₂ (%)	0	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40
ORF (%)	67.025	65.283	64.280	62.684	61.431	60.100	59.201	58.465	57.407

III.CONCLUSION

- ◆ CO₂ solubility in brine is a function of both pressure and temperature, with increase in pressure it increases and with reduce in temperature it increases.
- ◆ CO₂ solubility in brine decreases with increase in brine concentration.
- ◆ From the result, plotted between gas and oil recovery factor it can be concluded that the gas production during primary and secondary process produced is the gas produced as GOR with the oil but during tertiary recovery process the injected CO₂ has negative value which means it is dissolved in the brine.
- ◆ Well pattern has impact on oil recovery factor of the field which basically depends on different properties of the reservoir that which well pattern is more applicable to get a high recovery, in this study the seven spot well arrangement has a high oil recovery factor as compared to five and nine spot well arrangement. In seven spot well pattern the well distance is higher as compared to

- ◆ five and nine spot well pattern from the injection wells.
- ◆ Well distance of the production wells from the injection well also effects oil recovery factor of the field. A large distance from the injection well and even a small distance is also not suitable from the injection well. Therefore it is necessary to select an optimized well distance in order to obtain a high a recovery from the reservoir. In this study a distance of 257m is the optimized distance from the injection well.
- ◆ CO₂ concentration is also an important parameter which effects the oil recovery factor. The oil recovery factor is greater when the CO₂ concentration is 100% as compared to the gas composition when nitrogen is mixed with CO₂. Because when there is large amount of CO₂ injected there is more gas to swell the oil and increase the recovery and the nitrogen gas is not soluble in the oil that's why gives a low recovery.

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